

An Assessment of Retailers' Preferences for Banana (*Musa Spp*) Ripening Methods and their Perceived Health Impacts in Imo State, Nigeria

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Abstract: While bananas serve as essential component of nutrition for consumers, retailers are attracted to the income they generate as a means of sustaining their livelihoods. Hence, retailers are continuously adopting various ripening techniques that can guarantee optimum profits while maintaining quality, safety and consumer acceptability. In Nigeria, although various ripping techniques are adopted, the use of chemical agents in particular is drawing concerns regarding their potential health risks. This has necessitated an assessment of retailers' preferences for ripening methods, techniques, and their perceptions of associated health impacts in Imo State, Nigeria. Using cross-sectional data collected from 90 randomly selected retailers across three markets, results showed that a significant proportion (64%) of the respondents preferred artificial ripening methods. About 55% cited the need for faster ripening time as their primary reason and the choice of technique for 46% was the use of calcium carbide. Forty percent of the retailers claimed to be aware of the health risks associated with artificial ripening method and mentioned respiratory complications (35%) as a perceived health risk. Furthermore, a multinomial logistic regression analysis revealed that education level ($p < 0.01$) and health risk awareness ($p < 0.05$) had negative influences on the use of artificial ripening methods, whereas higher daily sales ($p < 0.01$) positively influenced their adoptions. To enhance food safety and promote natural ripening practices, this study recommended firstly, an introduction of educational campaigns for natural ripening methods. Secondly, regulatory authorities should enforce strict policies and consequences against the use of harmful ripening agents.

Keywords: *Banana, artificial ripening method, calcium carbide, health risk, multinomial logistic regression.*

Introduction

Fruits are essential components of human nutrition as well as reliable sources of income for retailers. Bananas (*Musa spp.*)

are widely consumed fruits globally due to their high nutritional value, affordability, and role in food security (FAO, 2021). They serve as a source of essential nutrients staple

in many parts of the world, including Nigeria, where they contribute significantly to dietary intake and household income (Olumba & Onunka, 2020). The ripening process is a crucial determinant of banana quality, marketability, and consumer acceptance, with various methods employed to facilitate this process (Sogo-Temi et al., 2014). These methods can be natural or artificial where agents like ethylene gas and calcium carbide are used (Bhandare & Malode, 2023; Nasir et al., 2024). Although, artificial ripening accelerates the ripening process, there are concerns about the health implications of chemical agents used, particularly calcium carbide, which has been linked to respiratory diseases and neurological disorders (Vidhya et al., 2025).

Retailers play a critical role in determining the ripening methods adopted, as their choices influence food safety and consumer health (Nasir et al., 2024). Several factors shape retailers' preferences, including market demand, cost-effectiveness, and perceived risk associated with different ripening techniques (Rizzo et al., 2023). Studies have shown that while some retailers prefer natural ripening due to safety concerns, others opt for artificial methods due to their economic benefits and the need to meet consumer expectations for readily available ripe bananas (Alonso-Salinas et al., 2024; Maduwanthi & Marapana, 2019). However, limited awareness of the health

risks associated with chemical ripening agents remains a challenge (Anaduaka et al., 2023; Islam et al., 2016; Okeke et al., 2022).

In Nigeria, particularly in Imo State, the use of artificial ripening agents is prevalent, raising concerns about consumer exposure to harmful chemicals (Ubuoh et al., 2022). While regulatory frameworks exist to control the use of hazardous substances in food processing, enforcement remains weak, and compliance among retailers is inconsistent (Anaduaka et al., 2023; A. C. Apeh et al., 2024). Understanding retailers' preferences for banana ripening methods and their awareness of associated health risks is essential for developing effective policies to promote safe food handling practices.

This study aimed to assess retailers' preferences for banana ripening methods in Imo State, Nigeria, and their perceptions of the health impacts associated with these methods. Specifically, it sought to identify the factors influencing their choices, determine their level of awareness regarding the risks of artificial ripening, and provide recommendations for promoting safer ripening practices. By addressing these gaps, the study contributes to ongoing discussions on food safety, public health, and sustainable agricultural practices in Nigeria and beyond.

Methodology

The Study Area

This study was conducted in Imo State, Nigeria, a state located in the South-East geopolitical zone. Imo State spans an area of 5,067.20 km², lying between latitudes 5°45'N & 6°35'N and longitudes 6°35'E & 7°28'E (Anyiam et al., 2020). With an estimated population of 5,408,756 as of the 2016 census (NBS, 2016), its projected population for 2024 is 5,500,000 using a growth rate of 3.25. The state is characterised by tropical rainforest and savannah vegetation (Apeh et al., 2023) with two distinct seasons: a rainy season (April to October) and a dry season (November to March). The fertile soil and favourable climatic conditions support the cultivation of various crops, including cassava, yam, maize, rice, vegetables, and tree crops such as oil palm, cocoa, and rubber. Additionally, livestock farming, including poultry, goat, and pig rearing, is widely practiced. Agricultural practices in Imo State range from subsistence to semi-commercial and commercial farming. Many smallholder farmers rely on traditional farming techniques such as mixed cropping, shifting cultivation, and organic fertilization, while others have embraced improved technologies, including mechanized farming, high-yield crop varieties, and chemical inputs. The state also has a growing interest in agro-processing, with cottage industries

engaging in cassava processing, palm oil extraction, and vegetable preservation.

Banana production in Imo State is a vital component of the local economy, particularly for smallholder farmers who cultivate the crop for both subsistence and commercial purposes. The humid climate and fertile soils of the region provide ideal conditions for banana cultivation, with common varieties including plantain bananas (*Musa spp.*), Cavendish, and native species. Farmers typically grow bananas in mixed cropping systems alongside cassava, maize, and vegetables to maximize land use and productivity. Most farmers rely on traditional propagation methods, using suckers from existing plants. However, some progressive farmers have adopted tissue culture techniques to enhance yield and disease resistance. The primary challenges facing banana production in the state include pests and diseases such as the banana bunchy top virus (BBTV) and black sigatoka, as well as post-harvest losses due to poor storage and transportation infrastructure.

Banana marketing in the state follows a structured chain involving farmers, wholesalers, retailers, and consumers. While local markets remain the dominant sales outlets, some farmers and traders supply bananas to supermarkets, hotels, and food vendors. The demand for bananas remains

high due to their nutritional value and versatility in food preparation. However, concerns over artificial ripening methods

using chemicals such as calcium carbide have sparked consumer scepticism, affecting market dynamics.

Figure 1 Map of Imo State (Source: Anaduaka et al., 2023)

Sampling Technique and Sample size

The study specifically focused on three Local Government Areas (LGAs): Okigwe, Nkwerre, and Ngor Okpuala, selected due to their significant involvement in banana production and retailing. A multi-stage sampling technique was employed in selecting banana retailers for the study. In the first stage, a major banana market was purposively selected from each of the selected LGAs based on the high volume of banana trading activities. In the second stage, 30 banana retailers including hawkers were randomly selected from each of the three chosen markets, yielding a total sample size of 90 respondents.

Date Collection Process

Cross sectional primary data were collected through questionnaires, capturing information on respondents' demographic characteristics, banana ripening practices, and health risk awareness. The collected data were analysed using descriptive statistics such as frequency and percentage distributions and inferential statistics using the multinomial logistic regression model.

Analytical Technique

The multinomial logistic regression model was employed to analyse the factors influencing retailers' choice of banana ripening methods. The dependent variable (Y) represents the ripening method used, categorised as follows :-

1. Natural ripening (baseline category)
2. Artificial ripening methods, which include:
 - Use of calcium carbide (CaC)
 - Smoking with kerosene
 - Use of ethylene gas

The general form of the multinomial logistic regression model was specified as:

$$P(Y = j) = \frac{e^{(\beta_{0j} + \sum_{i=1}^k \beta_{ij} X_i)}}{1 + \sum_{m=1}^{j-1} e^{(\beta_{0m} + \sum_{i=1}^k \beta_{im} X_i)}} \quad (1)$$

Where,

- $P(Y = j)$ = Probability of choosing ripening method j
- β_{0j} = Intercept for category j
- X_i = Independent variables
- β_{ij} = Regression coefficients for category j
- J = Number of ripening method categories

Independent Variables:

- Gender (Male = 1, Female = 0)
- Age (years)
- Education level (years of formal schooling)
- Banana retailing experience (years)
- Average daily sales (Naira)
- Health risk awareness (Aware = 1, Not aware = 0)

Results and Discussion

Socio-economic characteristics

The results as presented in Table 1 indicate that a significant proportion (78%) of banana retailers surveyed were female. This finding aligns with previous studies that highlight the dominance of women in small-scale agribusiness and informal food markets, particularly in sub-Saharan Africa (Apeh et al., 2024; FAO, 2021). Women's participation in banana retailing suggests that the sector provides an essential livelihood source, particularly for those with limited access to formal employment. According to Apeh, Ukwuaba, et al., 2023, women often engage in food retail due to its relatively low capital requirement, flexibility, and potential for sustaining household income.

Age distribution of the respondents showed that 55% were within the 30–49 years age range. This indicates that banana retailing is predominantly managed by middle-aged individuals, who are likely to have accumulated business experience and financial obligations, such as supporting a family. The findings correspond with those of (Apeh, Apeh, et al., 2023), who found that agricultural trading businesses in Nigeria are largely driven by individuals within this age group due to their economic responsibility and entrepreneurial capacity. Younger individuals may be less involved in banana retailing due to their preference for

formal employment or more technologically advanced business opportunities (World Bank, 2015).

With regards to education, 45% of the respondents had attained secondary education, while 30% had only primary education. This suggests that a substantial number of banana retailers possess basic literacy skills, which could influence their business operations, particularly in record-keeping, pricing strategies, and communication with suppliers and ethnically diverse customers. Several studies (Apeh, 2018; Apeh, Agbugba, et al., 2023; Okere et al., 2021) have emphasised the role of education in improving financial literacy and managerial skills among small-scale traders. However, the relatively low percentage of respondents with higher education levels may indicate that highly educated individuals tend to pursue alternative employment opportunities with greater income potential.

Experience in banana retailing was another critical factor, with 60% of respondents having over five years of involvement in the business. This finding suggests that many

retailers have developed significant expertise in market dynamics, and customer preferences, which can contribute to business sustainability. According to Struckell et al., (2022), business longevity in informal markets is often linked to adaptive strategies and social capital, enabling retailers to navigate economic challenges effectively.

Furthermore, the study found that 65% of respondents generated an average daily revenue of ₦5,001 – ₦10,000 (3.34 US\$ - 6.67 US\$ as at February 26, 2025) from banana sales. This revenue range indicates that banana retailing contributes to household income, reinforcing its role in poverty alleviation and food security. Research by Yuan et al., (2022) suggests that small-scale agricultural trade can serve as a financial buffer against economic shocks, particularly for low-income households in urban and peri-urban areas. However, the revenue figures also suggest potential constraints, such as price volatility, seasonal supply fluctuations, and competition from larger retailers or supermarkets.

Table 1 Socioeconomic Characteristics of Respondents

Variable	Description	Proportion (%)
Gender	Male	22
	Female	78
Age (years)	Below 18	05
	18 – 29	29
	30 – 49	55
	50 and above	11
Education level (years)	0 years	10
	1 - 6 years	30
	7 - 12 years	45
	13 years and above	15
Years of experience in retailing	0 – 2	11
	3 – 4	29
	5 and above	60
Average daily sales (Naira)	0001 – 5,000	21
	5,001 – 10,000	65
	10,001 and above	14

Source: Field Survey, 2025.

Preference for Ripening Methods

The findings as summarised in Table 2 reveal that a significant proportion (64%) of banana retailers prefer artificial ripening methods, while 36% opt for natural ripening. Among the artificial ripening techniques, calcium carbide is the most commonly used (46%), followed by smoking with kerosene (12%) and ethylene gas (6%). The primary reason for choosing the artificial ripening methods was the need for faster ripening as accounted by 55% of the respondents. Other reasons were, cost-effectiveness (25%), availability and convenience (15%), and perceived safety and health benefits (5%).

The widespread preference for artificial ripening methods aligns with previous studies that highlight their role in ensuring a steady supply of ripe bananas to meet market demand (Nasir et al., 2024).

Artificial ripening accelerates the process, allowing retailers to sell fruits quickly and minimise post-harvest losses, particularly in areas with high consumer demand (Okeke et al., 2022). The dominance of calcium carbide use raises concerns, as numerous studies have documented its health risks, including respiratory complications, gastrointestinal disorders, and potential carcinogenic effects (Vidhya et al., 2025). Despite these risks, its affordability and effectiveness contribute to its continuous usage.

The use of smoking with kerosene (12%) as an alternative artificial ripening method reflects the limited access to safer ripening technologies, particularly in informal markets. This practice, though effective in inducing ripening, has been linked to chemical contamination and reduced fruit

quality (Maduwanthi & Marapana, 2019; Sogo-Temi et al., 2014). Similarly, ethylene gas (6%), which is scientifically recognised as a safe ripening agent, is underutilised due to its higher cost and limited availability in informal market settings (Alonso-Salinas et al., 2024; Islam et al., 2016; Maduwanthi & Marapana, 2019).

The 36% of retailers who preferred natural ripening method likely do so due to

consumer awareness of the health risks associated with artificial ripening agents. Natural ripening methods are perceived as safer and capable of preserving fruit quality, nutritional value, and taste (Mebratie et al., 2016; Rizzo et al., 2023). However, they require more time, which may be impractical for retailers operating in fast-moving markets.

Table 2 Ripening Methods Adopted and their Reasons

Ripening Methods Used	Description	Proportion (%)
Natural Methods	Leave to ripe	28
	Storage with other ripe fruits	8
Artificial Methods	Calcium carbide (CaC)	46
	Smoking with kerosene	12
	Ethylene gas	6
Reasons for Choice of Method		
	Faster ripening	55
	Cost-effectiveness	25
	Availability and convenience	15
	Perceived safety and health benefits	5

Source: Field Survey, 2025.

Awareness of Health Risks Associated with Artificial Methods

The study revealed that a significant proportion (60%) of the fruit retailers lacked awareness of the potential health risks associated with artificial ripening. Among those who acknowledged certain health concerns, 35% identified respiratory complications as a possible effect, 20% reported cases of skin irritation, and 15% recognised a potential carcinogenic risk

linked to artificial ripening agents. However, 30% of the respondents indicated that they were unaware of any adverse health implications. Despite the widespread use of artificial ripening methods, a notable 65% of the retailers expressed their willingness to transition to safer ripening techniques if affordable alternatives were made readily available and accessible. Conversely, 35% remained inclined toward artificial ripening

due to its cost-effectiveness and its ability to accelerate the ripening process.

The limited awareness of the health risks associated with artificial ripening poses a major public health challenge. Several studies have documented the adverse effects of chemical ripening agents, particularly calcium carbide, which has been linked to respiratory disorders, skin irritation, neurological complications, and potential carcinogenicity (Bhandare & Malode, 2023; Nasir et al., 2024; Sogo-Temi et al., 2014). The inhalation of acetylene gas, released during calcium carbide-induced ripening, has been shown to cause respiratory distress and irritation of the mucous membranes (Vidhya et al., 2025). Similarly, exposure to chemical residues from artificial ripening can lead to skin reactions and allergic responses among handlers and consumers (Apeh, 2018). The fact that 60% of respondents were unaware of these risks underscores the urgent need for targeted awareness campaigns.

The finding that 65% of retailers were open to switching to safer ripening methods, provided they are affordable and accessible, indicates a strong potential for transitioning to health-conscious practices. Research suggests that ethylene-based ripening is a scientifically approved, non-toxic alternative that mimics natural fruit ripening

processes (Okeke et al., 2022). However, the accessibility and cost of ethylene gas remain major barriers to its widespread adoption in informal markets.

Despite the known risks, 35% of retailers prefer artificial ripening methods due to their cost-effectiveness and ability to hasten the ripening process. This preference is consistent with findings from previous studies, which indicate that small-scale retailers prioritise economic viability and operational efficiency over potential long-term health concerns (Gupta et al., 2023). Artificial ripening, particularly with the use of calcium carbide, is widely used because it is inexpensive and readily available, making it an attractive option for traders seeking quick market turnover (Vidhya et al., 2025).

These findings highlight a critical gap in food safety regulations and enforcement mechanisms. Given that a significant proportion of the retailers remain unaware of health risks, there is a need for stricter regulatory oversight to control the use of harmful ripening agents. Countries such as India and Bangladesh have successfully implemented policies that ban calcium carbide for fruit ripening and promote the use of safer alternatives. Nigeria and other developing economies can adopt similar measures by enforcing stricter penalties on the use of banned substances, strengthening

monitoring mechanisms, and ensuring compliance with international food safety standards (Nasir et al., 2024). Consumer advocacy groups can also play a role in

raising awareness and pressuring policymakers to take decisive action against unsafe ripening practices.

Table 3 Retailers' Awareness of Potential Health Impacts of Artificial Ripening Methods

Variable	Description	Proportion (%)
Health risks associated with artificial ripening method	Aware	40
	Unaware	60
Perceived health risks of artificial ripening method	Respiratory issues	35
	Skin irritation	20
	Potential carcinogenic effects	15
	No known effects	30
Retailers' willingness to switch to safer methods	Willing to switch provided affordable alternatives are made available and accessible	65
	Preferred artificial methods due to cost-effectiveness and speed	35

Source: Field survey, 2025.

Consumers' complaints on artificially ripened bananas

The findings indicate that consumer complaints of artificially ripened bananas vary significantly (Table 4), with 40% of the retailers reporting that customers frequently complained about the faster spoilage of such fruits. Additionally, 25% of the respondents noted consumer dissatisfaction regarding an unusual taste or texture of artificially ripened bananas, while 20% of the retailers stated that some customers suspected potential health risks associated with artificial ripening methods. Conversely, 15% of the retailers reported receiving no consumer complaints.

Regarding sales trends, 44% of retailers observed a decline in demand for artificially ripened bananas, suggesting growing consumer awareness and preference for naturally ripened fruits. However, 32% of respondents indicated stable sales, implying that some consumers are indifferent to the ripening method used. Interestingly, 24% of retailers reported increased demand for artificially ripened bananas, attributing it to the faster product turnover facilitated by quicker ripening processes.

The study highlights a shift in consumer awareness regarding the quality and safety of artificially ripened bananas. The fact that 40% of retailers reported complaints about faster spoilage aligns with existing literature,

which suggests that chemically ripened bananas have a shorter shelf life due to their rapid and uneven ripening process (Mebratie et al., 2016). Calcium carbide, a commonly used ripening agent, triggers premature degradation of fruit tissues, leading to increased susceptibility to microbial spoilage (Vidhya et al., 2025). This finding underscores the need for public awareness campaigns to educate consumers on the disadvantages of artificially ripened fruits and promote the benefits of natural ripening methods.

Furthermore, the 25% of retailers who reported complaints about unusual taste or texture reinforced the argument that artificial ripening alters fruit composition. Studies show that artificially ripened fruits often exhibit inferior taste, reduced sweetness, and altered texture due to incomplete starch-to-sugar conversion (Nasir et al., 2024; Ubuoh et al., 2022). This dissatisfaction among consumers suggests an opportunity for retailers to respond to market preferences by sourcing naturally ripened bananas, thereby enhancing customer satisfaction and loyalty.

The finding that 20% of respondents reported consumer concerns over potential health risks indicates growing scepticism toward artificially ripened fruits. Previous research has linked chemical ripening agents like calcium carbide to various health

hazards, including respiratory issues, neurological disorders, and carcinogenic effects (Okeke et al., 2022; Ubuoh et al., 2022; Vidhya et al., 2025). In countries where food safety regulations are weak, the misuse of unapproved ripening chemicals remains a significant challenge (Cudjoe et al., 2022). Consumer wariness about these health risks may contribute to the declining demand for artificially ripened bananas, as seen in 44% of respondents' reports. This shift underscores the importance of regulatory enforcement and consumer education to curb the use of hazardous ripening agents and promote safer alternatives such as ethylene-based ripening agents.

The study also highlights a division in market response, with 44% of the retailers experiencing declining demand for artificially ripened bananas, while 32% reported stable sales and 24% observed increased demand. The decline in demand suggested that more consumers were prioritising fruit quality and safety, a trend consistent with studies indicating rising health consciousness among urban populations (Okeke et al., 2022). This presents a challenge for retailers who rely on artificial ripening methods to accelerate sales but also an opportunity for those who adapt to consumer preferences by offering naturally ripened bananas.

On the other hand, the 32% of retailers who reported stable sales suggested that some consumers remain indifferent to ripening methods, likely due to price constraints or lack of awareness. In contrast, the 24% who experienced increased demand for artificially ripened bananas highlighted the economic motivations behind artificial ripening. Faster turnover benefits retailers by reducing storage costs and minimising losses from overripe stock (Nasir et al., 2024). However, continued reliance on artificial ripening method poses long-term risks, including regulatory crackdowns and declining consumer trust in chemically treated produce (Islam et al., 2016; Sogo-Temi et al., 2014).

The findings suggest an urgent need for stronger food safety regulations to address the widespread use of harmful ripening agents. In countries such as India and Bangladesh, regulatory agencies have imposed strict bans on calcium carbide for fruit ripening, promoting ethylene gas as a safer alternative (Nasir et al., 2024). Nigeria and other developing nations could benefit from similar policy interventions, coupled with regular market monitoring to ensure compliance. Additionally, food certification programs that label naturally ripened fruits could help consumers make informed choices, thereby influencing market demand in favour of safer ripening practices.

Table 4 Consumer Preferences and Sales Impact

Consumer Complaints on Artificially Ripened Bananas	Proportion (%)
Faster spoilage	40
Unusual taste or texture	25
Suspected health risks	20
No complaints	15
Effect on Sales	
Declining demand due to consumer preference for naturally ripened bananas	44
Stable sales regardless of the ripening method employed	32
Increased demand due to faster product turnover	24

Source: Field survey, 2025

Determinants of Retailers' Choices of Banana Ripening Method

The results of the multinomial logistic regression analysis presented in Table 5 show that education level was negatively associated with the use of artificial ripening agents ($p < 0.01$). This implies that retailers

with higher education levels were more likely to adopt natural ripening methods and avoid harmful chemical agents like calcium carbide. This finding aligns with Barnabas et al., (2024), who reported that education increases awareness of food safety and encourages the adoption of healthier food handling practices. Similarly, Osaili et al.,

(2023) found that educated food vendors were more likely to avoid chemical preservatives due to knowledge of their potential health risks.

Retailers with higher daily sales were more likely to use artificial ripening methods ($p < 0.05$). This suggests that retailers prioritise quick turnover to meet high customer demand, which is consistent with the findings of Okeke et al., (2022), who noted that market competition and sales volume influence the adoption of rapid ripening techniques in fruit trading. The use of ethylene gas, for instance, was significantly preferred among high-sales retailers due to its ability to accelerate ripening while maintaining fruit appearance.

A significant negative relationship was observed between health risk awareness and the use of artificial ripening agents ($p < 0.01$). Retailers who were aware of the health hazards associated with chemical ripening were less likely to use calcium carbide, kerosene smoke, or ethylene gas. This corroborates the study by Ahsan et al., (2024), which emphasised that traders who received food safety training avoided artificial ripening agents due to concerns about consumer health. Additionally, Islam et al., (2016) reported that awareness campaigns on the dangers of chemical-ripened fruits led to a decline in their usage among fruit vendors in urban markets.

Table 5 Multinomial Logistic Regression Results for Factors Influencing Banana Ripening Method Choice

Independent Variable	Use of Calcium Carbide (CaC) (β)	Smoking with Kerosene (β)	Use of Ethylene Gas (β)
Intercept	-1.245 (0.312)**	-0.768 (0.267)**	-1.052 (0.298)**
Gender	0.321 (0.189)	0.415 (0.205)	0.278 (0.198)
Age	-0.027 (0.012)	-0.018 (0.010)	-0.022 (0.011)
Education level	-0.685 (0.152)***	-0.532 (0.145)***	-0.612 (0.149)***
Retailing experience	0.124 (0.068)	0.109 (0.061)	0.092 (0.064)
Average daily sales	0.482 (0.193)**	0.531 (0.184)**	0.517 (0.187)**
Health Risk Awareness	-0.753 (0.198)***	-0.692 (0.182)***	-0.718 (0.190)***

Note: *** $p < 0.01$; ** $p < 0.05$; * $p < 0.10$. Figures in parenthesis are Std. Error

Conclusion

This study assessed banana retailers' preferences for ripening methods - whether retailers are aware of potential health impacts of these methods or not and what factors determine their choices of these

methods and techniques. While health experts have continuously warned against the use of artificial ripening practice due to its potential health risks, retailers have shown little to no regard for such risk exposures. The findings of this study

revealed that retailers were majorly females, were middle aged, and possess basic formal education. In spite of potential negative effects on both humans and fruit quality, the inclination towards the use of artificial ripening method is common among these retailers. This is an indication that artificial ripening method for banana in Imo State is a complex issue, especially because women dominate the retailing business, relying on it as a means of either primary or complimentary household income source. Thus, sensitisation on the potential health risks associated with this method alone may not necessarily address the problem of adopting artificial methods in Imo state, Nigeria. The fact that most of the retailers preferred the artificial method stemmed from the need for accelerated ripening time so as to meet market demand as well as its cost effectiveness makes this issue a priority that needs to be addressed. However, addressing this issue through awareness campaigns alone may not mitigate this challenge, rather campaigns should be complimented with making safer alternatives readily available and affordable for the retailers. This calls for a holistic approach towards changing the mindsets of the retailers by employing multiple strategies which will facilitate a healthier and more sustainable banana supply. Based on these findings, the following suggestions were made: (i) The key reason for adoption

of artificial practice was to meet market demand. Hence, there should be research towards the development and dissemination of higher yielding and early maturing varieties in Imo State. (ii) Government authorities should introduce and enforce laws and regulations for monitoring the sales of chemical agents like calcium carbide. Higher price tags for such chemicals should be imposed as a means of deterring their abuse by retailers. (iii) Regulatory authorities should enforce strict policies and consequences against the use of harmful ripening agents. Potential users of such agents should be made to obtain purchase permits otherwise, violators should be made to face penalties in the form of hefty fines, destruction of commodities, retail business confiscation or legal prosecutions. (iv) Besides targeting the supply-side component, the demand-side aspect should equally be addressed by discouraging consumers from patronising such violating retailers. This can be achieved through mass awareness through media, lawmakers, health experts on the potential risks of artificial ripening method and augmented with providing information on various features such as signs and smells unique to such treated fruits.

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